

THE PRACTICAL IMPORTANCE OF CREATING ELECTRONIC DICTIONARIES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13220060>

With the introduction of information technology (IT) into educational process the use of electronic dictionaries, mobile apps, and web applications is considered to be relevant and gains popularity. One of the primary teaching tasks is to develop the student's ability to comprehend lexical units and apply them in foreign language learning.

It should be noted that currently there are several notions and terms connected with electronic dictionaries. Most of them are synonyms and can be used interchangeably. In modern papers and publications, we came across: electronic dictionary, e-dictionary, digital dictionary. The words application, resource and tool are sometimes used in the meaning of "dictionary". The terminology is clear enough and there are usually no difficulties in interpreting or understanding it. We use the mentioned terminology in our research as well.

Electronic dictionaries, or digital lexicons, have become indispensable tools in our digitally driven world. Their creation holds significant importance across various fields and for diverse purposes, underpinned by these theoretical perspectives:

1. Access & Accessibility:

- **Democratization of Knowledge:** Electronic dictionaries break down geographical and financial barriers, making knowledge readily available to anyone with internet access. They democratize access to language resources, aiding literacy and education in underserved communities.
- **Inclusivity and Diversity:** Digital dictionaries can incorporate diverse languages, dialects, and cultural nuances, fostering inclusivity and promoting the preservation of endangered languages. They can also cater to specific needs of individuals, such as learners with disabilities, providing accessible formats and functionalities.
- **Accessibility for the Deaf & Hard of Hearing:** Dictionaries with multimedia components, like audio and video, can benefit individuals with hearing impairments, offering visual and auditory representations of words and concepts.

2. Evolutionary Dynamics & Learning:

- **Dynamic and Iterative:** Electronic dictionaries are continuously evolving. They can be updated with new words, meanings, and usage examples, reflecting the dynamism of language. This allows users to stay abreast of linguistic changes and evolving vocabulary.
- **Personalized Learning:** Digital platforms offer features like personalized word lists, progress tracking, and interactive exercises, enhancing the learning experience. This caters to individual learning styles and fosters deeper engagement with language.
- **Multimodal Learning:** Electronic dictionaries can incorporate images, audio, video, and interactive elements, creating a richer and more engaging learning experience. This multimodal approach enhances comprehension and retention of vocabulary.

Creating electronic dictionaries in English and Uzbek holds significant practical importance for various reasons:

1. Accessibility and Convenience

- **Instant Access:** Electronic dictionaries provide immediate access to definitions, synonyms, antonyms, and translations, making it easier for users to find information quickly.
- **Portability:** Users can access electronic dictionaries on smartphones, tablets, or computers, allowing for learning on the go.

2. Language Learning and Proficiency

- **Bilingual Support:** For Uzbek speakers learning English and vice versa, electronic dictionaries facilitate better understanding and learning of vocabulary, grammar, and usage.
- **Pronunciation Guides:** Many electronic dictionaries include audio pronunciations, which help learners master correct pronunciation.

3. Cultural Exchange

- **Understanding Context:** Electronic dictionaries can provide cultural notes, idiomatic expressions, and contextual usage, enriching the user's understanding of both languages.
- **Promoting Language Learning:** They encourage language exchange and interaction between English and Uzbek speakers.

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